

A Systematic Analysis of the Organizational Development Theory and Transtheoretical Framework in Weight Management

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Abstract: An integrated treatment theory that assesses a person's readiness to form a new, better habit and offers tools, or change processes, to help them do so is the transtheoretical model of behavior modification. Self-efficacy, decisional balance, levels, processes, and phases of transformation are among the elements of the paradigm. The transtheoretical model is also known as the "stages of change," however this is a synecdoche as the stages of change only make up a small portion of the model, which also includes processes, degrees of change, and other components.

Index Terms – Systematic, Weight, Management, Organizational.

I. INTRODUCTION:

The cognitive approach of behavior change is an integrated therapy theory that evaluates a person's preparedness to develop a new, better habit and provides strategies, or change processes, to assist them in doing so. The components of the paradigm include self-efficacy, decisional balance, and levels, processes, and stages of change. The term "stages of change" is another name for the transtheoretical model, although it is a synecdoche because the stages of change are only one part of the model, which also contains processes, degrees of change, and other elements.

The TTM is a paradigm, not a theory, and depending on how well they work, alternative theoretical concepts and constructs can be used at different levels of the model. According to the TTM, people experience six stages of change: pre-contemplation, contemplation, preparation, action, maintenance, and termination. The original paradigm did not contain termination, and it is used less commonly when applying stages of change to habits relevant to one's health. In order to move people through the model to maintenance, the ideal level of behavior for each stage of change, several intervention strategies are most successful.

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II. STAGES OF CHANGE OR FRAMEWORK OF TRANSTHEORETICAL:

1. **Pre-contemplation.** The initial phase of change is preparation stage. Pre-contemplation is the phase before people begin to think about a change. People who are in this stage are referred to as "in denial" since they insist that their conduct is not a problem. At this point, people could not be aware of how detrimental their behaviors are or they might

not be fully aware of the effects of their choices. If you're at this stage, you can feel resigned to your present circumstance or think you have little influence over your behavior.

2. **Consideration:** At this point, people start to become more conscious of the possible advantages of making a change, but the costs start to stand out even more. When it comes to change, this conflict significantly increases one's sensation of unease. Due to this uncertainty, the contemplation phase of change may last months or even years. The stage of introspection is one that many individuals never leave.
3. **Preparation:** During the planning stage, you might start making little adjustments to get ready for a significant life shift. For instance, you could choose to consume lower-fat meals if you wish to reduce weight. You might try switching brands or cutting back on your daily cigarette intake if you wish to stop smoking. You might also take a proactive stance, such as visiting a therapist, signing up for a fitness centre, or reading self-help books. There are a number of things you can do to improve your chances of making a successful life change if you're still in the planning phases. Gather as much knowledge as you can on how to change your behavior. Create a list of quotes that motivate you. Create a list of your goals. Locate mentors and cheerleaders, such as friends, counselors, or support groups.
4. **Taking Action:** At the fourth phase of change, people start acting proactively to accomplish their goals. Because the prior steps were not given enough consideration or time, resolutions typically fail. For instance, many people resolve to lose weight in the New Year and start a new exercise regimen, better diet, and snack-reduction strategy right away. Since the earlier steps were skipped, these decisive actions are essential to success yet are typically dropped after only a few weeks. If you're currently working toward a goal, praise yourself and treat yourself for any successful actions you've performed. It is impossible to overestimate the role that support and encouragement play in keeping favourable improvements in place. To maintain your commitment and confidence in your abilities, take the time to regularly evaluate your motives, resources, and progress.
5. **Maintenance:** The maintenance phase of the Stages of Change concept involves successfully avoiding old behaviors while upholding new ones. If you're attempting to keep up a new habit, look for methods to ward against temptation. Add more positive actions to replace negative ones. Give yourself a treat when you successfully prevent a relapse. If you fail, don't be too harsh on one or give it up. Think on how small of a setback that was instead. Relapses are frequent and a necessary part of undergoing a lifelong metamorphosis, as you will discover during the next stage. The belief that one can continue their change at this stage increases.
6. **Relapse:** Any attempt to change a habit will always end in relapse. You can feel as though you've failed, let yourself down, or are frustrated when you relapse. Restarting the behavioral management procedure at the planning, action, or maintenance phases is the best course of action, even when relapses are challenging to overcome. You may wish to reevaluate your strategies and tools. Reiterate your reasons for doing things, your plan, and your commitment to your goals. Plan out how you will resist temptation in the future. Resolutions fail when insufficient planning and implementation are done. If you tackle a goal with an awareness of how to effectively prepare, act, and sustain a new behavior, you'll be much more likely to achieve it.

III. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE TRANSTHEORETICAL MODEL:

The process of health planning includes the exciting step of creating a health intervention. On the other side, an intervention does not suggest that you create ideas from the beginning and then spread them around a community. Making an intervention involves much more than that! Yes, being creative when creating intervention activities is a plus, but if you want your health intervention to be effective at altering health behavior, you must understand health theories and know how to apply them.

IV. ORGANIZATIONAL CHANGE CONCEPT IN WEIGHT MANAGEMENT EMERGENCE:

A change in health behavior is necessary to control obesity. There is growing body of research on the variables that influence the adoption and maintenance of health behaviors due to their complexity, the creation and running tests of theories that conceptualize the relationships between these variables and health behaviors, and the implementation of these variables in successful behavior change interventions while taking into account the content (methods) and delivery characteristics. Following a brief review of developments in behavior change research theories and methods with an emphasis on the management of obesity, a discussion of the main challenges facing the area is presented.

The emergence and quick development of the field of health behavior change is a response to the urgent need to comprehend the complexity underlying people's choices and participation in activities that influence their health and very well, including sustained weight control. Health behavior change interventions (HBCIs), which take into consideration issues like difficulty and desire for change, have the potential to improve the health of communities if produced in large quantities and carefully targeted. Context sensitivity is critical since interventions are meant to be used in the real world. In other words, the effectiveness of an intervention is evaluated by how well it can address a problem in a particular environment for a certain target population and with a specific behavioral outcome in mind. In this succinct narrative review, we will discuss some of the latest research topics in the field of health behavior change, with a particular emphasis on the management of obesity. These topics include the application of formal theories and appropriate forethought of their mechanism of action, the choice of behavior change strategies used in HBCIs, and the implementation of technology to encourage sustained behavior change.

V. CONCLUSION:

To recognize and comprehend change in both yourself and others, the Steps of Model Of change might be useful. Even though the Steps of Change Model has many drawbacks, it can help you visualize your own change processes so you know what to anticipate when trying to break a habit. There is a corpus of rigorous scientific research in the field of weight management that aims to discover and advance our knowledge of the best practices for developing, implementing, and evaluating HBCIs. Researchers have looked at practical methods for helping interventionists "speak the same language" by creating a variety of taxonomies and frameworks. Despite the fact that this field has made tremendous advancements, there are still many unanswered problems and challenges that need to be resolved, as seen by the wide range of HBCI effects and the limited findings of meta-analyses looking at interactions across interventional factors. One recent attempt in the area of health behavior change science to support evidence-based practice is the Human Behavior-Change Project by Michael and colleagues.

REFERENCE:

1. "Home - NCBI - PMC." Website: www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov.in, Home – PMC
2. Wikipedia: "Transtheoretical Model." Wikipedia, "Transtheoretical Model," en.wikipedia.org, accessed March 19, 2009.
3. Transtheoretical Model (or Stages of Change) - Change in Health Behavior www.prochange.com, 7 April 2022; Prochange.Com.
4. "The 6 Stages of Behavior Change" is number two. 28 July 2021, Verywell Mind, www.verywellmind.com.
5. Application of Transtheoretical Model on Behavioral Changes, and Amount of Physical Activity Among University Students, Liu, Kien Ting, et al. *Frontiers*, 1 January 2001;
6. www.frontiersin.org; 7 April 2022;
7. www.prochange.com.